

BM-5102: ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR
SEMESTER 1 2020/2021

SELF-REFLECTIVE CRITIQUE REPORT
20M1303

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1. OVERVIEW

Master of Management (MM) programme is a course in Universiti Brunei Darussalam (MM) offered to qualified graduates that is inspire to pursue their studies after taking Bachelor Degree. The course is intended to develop an intellectual skill of graduate and providing valuable knowledge in general and strategic management for the students. The program is conducted for at least 3 semesters starting from August and expected to be finish by the end of November a year after. My desire to pursue master started when I realise there is a high number of unemployment which make me consider to continue my studies on a higher level. At the same time I realise that I should just continue my studies fearing that I may not have the time or willingness to continue my studies in the near future after I got a job. At first, I was interested to apply in several universities abroad that also includes applying scholarship offered by Korean and Japanese Embassy. After applying in those institution and international agencies, I thought that it will not be any harm to pursue masters in local university as well and chooses MM as the main course that I am interested as it can broaden my knowledge in Management sectors as it is seen as beneficial in workplace. However, there is also some thoughts that hinders me from pursuing MM as I believe that it might be difficult for me to shift from an individual that practically indulge himself with History and international studies suddenly change its scope to Management yet little that I Know about Business as I do not have any business background to begin with. Regardless, my strong will to pursue Masters has allowed me to take MM and believe that I may learn something valuable for my future career.

Organisational Behaviour is one of the core modules that is needed to be taken by MM students. At first, I was quite lost with the outline and expectation that should be ace by the students from our first lecture. This might be the fact that we are conducting our class in a virtual manner which is quite discouraging for me to study and keep up with the lectures delivered by the lecturer. As time goes by, I slowly understand the concept of the module and has develop myself to think critically and be independent. This module allows me to understand my initial thoughts and desire on my personal motivation of pursuing MM. This type of activity has enlightened me to be more proactive in all the activities both in academics and other types of work that I am engaging in. This module also thought me to be prepared and ready for any upcoming assignments given by the lecturer believing that each assignment actually has sharpened my knowledge and making sure that we are on track on our assignment. It also has given me an interesting knowledge of humans behaviour based on theories that is something new to me.

After finishing the module on my first semester of Master's Degree, I realize that it is quite beneficial for me as the things that I have learned in lectures and personal research that is related to the module has given me a new broader knowledge of perspective. As an individual coming from history and international studies major, it surely is tough for me to adapt with new perspective of education yet it is still manageable and it is really interesting for me. It also has encouraged me to be more aware with the surroundings and learn new things. The module taught me not to be dependable and be creative in every decision-making that I have made throughout the course. I am also considered myself as a lucky individual for having some supportive colleagues that always giving me constant support and help one another to complete our assignment given for this module despite having mental health issue from time to time. I would also like to highlight all of groupmates in this module for always keeping up with each other and their eagerness to complete our group assignments with no issues and tension arise from one another but instead it enhances our close relations despite being a total stranger with one another.

2. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE

Theoretical knowledge provides a deeper understanding of a concept that teaches the theory of knowledge, reasoning and technique on how certain as it helps to understand why one technique is successful than the others (Ramnani, 2017). On the other hand, Practical knowledge is based on day to day experiences that is gained by doing certain things that is constructed on real life experience and tasks given.

Ever since online learning is widely conducted by all the lecturers in the university, students find it hard to cope with the new learning style that has been implemented. This has made the students to lose their interest to concentrate on their virtual classes as they were distracted with other things such as background noises, other temptations to be out of focus by doing other things, technical issues and the virtual setting is conducted at the comfort of the student's preferences. Therefore, this is an issue for the students to be more attentive to the virtual lectures as it affected students' performance in class. However, it reflects back on my personal intention on why I pursue my masters which relates to personal motivation in continuing my studies from a Bachelor Degree holder to a Master's Degree.

Motivation is defined as the degree to which individuals commit effort to achieve goals that they perceive as being meaningful and worthwhile (Johnson & Johnson, 2003). It is important to understand the underlying motivation factors of an individual to further understand their behavior. One of the basic motivation theories that is applicable to me would be the cognitive evaluation theory which looks at the difference of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of an individual. According to SpriggrHR (2020), intrinsic indicates an act of doing that is interesting and enjoyable while, extrinsic looks at the behavior of a person to perform task and learn new skill because of rewards or to avoid punishment. The intrinsic motivation of me to take Master's degree of Management and be attentive in virtual classes is because I desire to learn new knowledge that can be useful for my career path, meanwhile my extrinsic motivate could be the rewards I would be getting such as getting a good job after finishing my module that gave one step forward to the completion of my Master's Degree.

Types of Motivation	Example of my personal motivation
Intrinsic motivation	Desire to expand my knowledge that can be useful for my career path
Extrinsic motivation	By finishing the core module, it gave me a sense of accomplishment and important step towards the completion of Master Degree that significantly would upgrade my qualification of education which can enhance more chances of getting a good job with a higher salary than a bachelor degree holder upon completion of the course.

Figure 1: Cognitive Evaluation Theory in completing my Master's Degree

3. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

My contributions on our group assignments is making sure that our case study is relevant and applicable for us to pursue without any difficulties based on our capabilities to ensure success in completing the case study. I am also in-charge of conducting every single meeting for our group with the purpose to discuss our progress and things that can be done as a team to ensure that we manage to accomplish before the deadline, sharing some relevant ideas for our case study, also responsible for making surveys for our research by using google forms. Since the group case study is based on first come first serve basis, I am lucky enough to have a good case study that is based on the current situation that is of my initial interest to begin with. This become possible because of my team's effort, eagerness and their quick response in choosing the best relatable case study that surely will be beneficial for us.

4. OPINIONS OF TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENTS

My group comprises of four team members namely, Khairunnisa, Liyana, Syhadah and myself that surprisingly cooperating well with one another. We managed to perform well in every single necessary task that we planned together to ensure consistency result and high performance in completing the task given. This is quite interesting for me as we started from being a total stranger yet our outcome and strong connection that we build as allow us to complete our case study with ease. Our allocation of tasks has proved that planning is quite important for us and it surely has smoothen our progress. According to Nisa, she mentions that due to my personal connection and a big circle of friends it significantly made us to gain easy to access information. She also added that I always have interesting idea that can be used in our case study. Meanwhile, Liyana states that I always know what to do, always have some interesting points that can be added to the case study despite my last-minute work that is always dreadful and exciting. Her claim is supported by Syhadah that also agrees that my last-minute work has brought significant outcomes and breathtaking. She also added that my big circle of friends and my socialization skills with others allowed us to gather responds/ feedbacks needed for the survey questions. Moreover, 75 to 80% of responses from both local and international students literally came from my circle of friends. Consequently, we were able to gather the information/feedback thanks to him.

5. OUTCOME OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

The outcome of our group assignment is considered a success. We have formed a good teamwork since the beginning till the end. We managed to complete different types of roles and task given to us with no difficulty. We also manage to surpass our initial attention to complete our case study weeks before the deadline, it is all thanks to our dedication and good communication of the team. The concept of teamwork, understandable, cohesive and responsive are hugely emphasize in our group that has allowed our team to ace every single work that could be done. We also have no issues and complications with one another as we believe it will only create a bad vibe with one another. Furthermore, our case study has given us some useful knowledge of us in this new education meeting that is currently the new normal education mode that has been set by the

university to limit the spread of the global pandemic of COVID19. It also has given us useful information that can be relatable to our daily lives.

In addition to that, even though our topic on how the global pandemic of COVID19 has affected students' performance that is mainly focusing on local students in national universities, we managed to do some comparison by creating a different survey that is specifically for other international students studying in other universities. This shows how the team is always eager to gain information that can be useful for us.

6. INDIVIDUAL STRENGTH AND WEAKNESSES

After completing this module with both individual and group assignments, there are some strengths and weaknesses that I have experienced in the journey. First of all, my strength is having personal connection that allows me to be stress-free without having to think hard on what the topic is going to be for my individual assignment. It significantly helped me to be confident with myself with what I am going to propose in this module. My experiences in leadership, social and communication skills significantly helped me to complete all the assignments given in this module. I also have the tendency not to be panic and always have solution to any unexpected hurdles thanks to my imaginative and creative thinking. I also does not have to appeal for my individual analysis research paper despite having some problems with the faculty in getting through with personal research on using primary source as I am quite close with the founder of the company and gave full support in whatever research that I was planning to do at his company.

Challenges that I have experience throughout this module started off with my community work, part time jobs and other commitments that hinders me to give my full potential in delivering all my work in a very good manner. I always make myself busy with all the social community project that I personally coordinated which has brought me to represent Brunei for several times in some international conferences. I also have a part-time job which subsequently leading myself with less free time to spare. Furthermore, my personal commitment is also another factor that lead me to think that at times I cannot really give my full dedication to all my assignments. Despite all this, I have encountered several breakdowns in the semester with the issue of deteriorating mental health problems due to some traumatic personal problems that are really discouraging for me to continue my studies.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CHANGES

Teamwork is key to success in every single group assignment. Thus, it is essential for all the team member to emphasize the need to cooperate with one another. I also believe that transparency is also crucial in a group assignment because we get to know the problems faced by the team members. It is also important to be verbal with one another regardless whether there might a possibility of clash interest because in this way we get to know different opinions that might be useful for our report. Meanwhile, as for the changes that can be done is to change my work etiquette in all of the assignments that I have regardless whether it is an individual or group assignments. I am the type of student who enjoys doing his assignment on the last minute because it makes me more dedicated, focused and had a huge desire to complete the task prior to the deadline that has been set by the lecturer. At the same time, I was having mental health issues which demotivates

me to finish up all the assignments early even before the deadline. However, I believe that it should be change in the future because we as students needs to be more responsive and acts quickly that is certainly can be an advantage for us and can adaptable to our future career.

8. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REFLECTIVE REPORT

According to John Zubizarreta (2008), reflection report is a process where students gets to reflect back and describe their personal learning experience throughout the entire course or module that has been taken by the student. The report is quite important for students to understand what they have been through and find ways on how to improve themselves in the future. It can be beneficial for the students to keep track on their progress and also at the same try to find ways to fix any flaws that has been encountered by the students. Personally, reflective report is really important for me to reflect back what I have contributed in my group assignment and it is a good method for me to indulge on my learning experience in the module. Furthermore, reflective report is quite relatable to our peer review that has been set by the lecturer which subsequently given us an opportunity to get feedback from our colleagues on our assignments that can be useful for me to fix any possible mistakes that has been pointed out by our friends. Moreover, I believe that this reflective report is a good way for students as it helps to understand deeply their learning experiences and taught them to learn from their experience and get better in the future.

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